

1 Food insecurity moderates the acute effect of subjective
2 socioeconomic status on food consumption

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18 Abstract

19 Experimentally inducing low subjective socioeconomic status (SSES) increases food consumption in
20 standardized eating opportunities. Separately, food insecurity (FI) has also been shown to be
21 associated with increased opportunistic food consumption. Here, we assigned 123 adult volunteers to
22 a low-SSES manipulation or a control condition, followed by an opportunity to consume snack foods.
23 We measured FI prior to the experiment. Thus, our experiment served to replicate the effects of SSES
24 and of FI on consumption, and also to establish whether these effects combine additively or
25 interactively. The low-SSES manipulation increased food consumption, but only among participants
26 who were food-secure at baseline. Amongst food-insecure participants, the effect was reversed. This
27 interaction was not predicted a priori and is presented as an exploratory finding. We also found
28 evidence that both SSES and FI affected the hedonic evaluation of the snack foods. Our findings
29 suggest that both FI and low SSES affect the consumption and evaluation of food. Their combined
30 effects on consumption may be complex.

31 **Keywords:** Food insecurity; socioeconomic status; obesity; eating; energy intake

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33 **Introduction**

34 Low socioeconomic status is a predictor of obesity and overweight in developed countries, especially
35 amongst women (McLaren, 2007; Newton et al., 2017; Sobal and Stunkard, 1989). Subjective
36 socioeconomic status (SSES; the self-assessed appraisal of one's position within society) explains
37 variation in obesity above and beyond more socioeconomic objective variables (Goodman et al.,
38 2001, 2003). Recently, researchers have begun to manipulate SSES experimentally, using tasks that
39 cause participants to compare their lot favourably or unfavourably to others. Such manipulations
40 increase intended or actual food consumption in their immediate aftermath (Bratanova et al., 2016;
41 Cardel et al., 2015; Cheon and Hong, 2016; Sim et al., 2018a), and increase secretion of the hormone
42 ghrelin (Sim et al., 2018b), lending support to the idea that the relationship between SSES and body
43 weight may be causal, and mediated by energy intake.

44 Food insecurity (FI)—the limited or uncertain ability to procure adequate food—also predicts obesity
45 and overweight amongst women (Nettle et al., 2017; Townsend et al., 2001). In two recent studies,
46 food-insecure participants consumed more calories when given free eating opportunities (Nettle et al.,
47 2019; Stinson et al., 2018). Thus, two factors appear to predict how much a person will eat when
48 given a staged opportunity: their (experimentally manipulated) SSES; and their (baseline) FI. As these
49 factors have only recently been documented, they require replication. It is currently unknown how
50 they combine. It is plausible that they would be additive: people who are food-insecure consume more
51 than those who are food-secure, and both consumption of both groups is increased by the same
52 amount by manipulation of low SSES. Alternatively, there could be interactions between the
53 manipulation and FI. Food-insecure participants might show a larger response to the experimental
54 SSES manipulation; this would be a form of sensitization to acute cues indicative of shortfall or stress.
55 Equally, food-insecure participants might show a smaller response to the SSES manipulation, because
56 their calorie consumption in the control condition would be higher anyway.

57 As well as finding that food-insecure women consumed more than food-secure women, Nettle et al
58 (2019) found that food-insecure women rated one of the foods (chocolate) more highly when asked to
59 evaluate it. Thus, an important proximate psychological effect of FI may be to increase the hedonic
60 value of foods, leading to greater consumption, as suggested by Anselme and Güntürkün (2018). Just
61 as FI might lead to changes in the hedonic value of foods, so might SSES. That is, the increased
62 consumption seen following SSES manipulations might be due to changes in the perception of the
63 hedonic value of the foods on offer. This possibility has not been tested in previous studies.

64 The present study is a conceptual replication of Nettle et al (2019), in which we measured baseline FI
65 in a community sample, and then presented a mock 'taste test' of snack foods, and measured energy
66 intake. The innovation of the present study was that we also included an SSES manipulation
67 (following the methods of Cheon and Hong, 2016). Hence, our study also provides a replication of the
68 acute experimental effect of SSES on consumption. Based on prior findings, we made the following
69 confirmatory predictions: there will be an interaction between sex and FI in predicting consumption,
70 with food-insecure women consuming more than food-secure women, but no difference by FI
71 amongst men; and participants receiving the low-SSES manipulation will consume more than
72 participants in a control condition. We investigated the possibility of interactions between FI and
73 manipulated SSES, but without directional prediction. We also predicted that both FI and SSES would
74 affect the hedonic value of the foods on offer, as reflected in participant ratings.

75 **Materials and Methods**

76 *Ethics statement*

77 Ethical approval for this study was granted by the Faculty of Medical Sciences ethics committee at
78 Newcastle University, approval number 1400/15594/2017. All participants gave written informed
79 consent to participate and were debriefed as to the true nature of the study on completion.

80 *Data availability*

81 The raw data from this study, along with R code used for analysis, are freely available via the Zenodo
82 repository at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2580973>.

83 *Participants*

84 We recruited an opportunity sample of 125 adult participants (36 males, 89 females; 84 students) via
85 flyers, online advertisement and registers held at Newcastle University. Two male participants did not
86 complete key parts of the study, leaving 123 (34 males, 89 females). This gave a power of 0.96 to
87 detect the SSES effect size in Cheon and Hong (2016)'s study 3, and 0.75 to detect the effect size in
88 their study 4. Participants were asked to disclose any food allergies or intolerances that might affect
89 their participation in the taste test, and none were excluded for this reason. The study was presented as
90 an investigation of how individual characteristics and eating patterns relate to food preferences.

91 *Food insecurity*

92 Participants completed an online questionnaire prior to attending the laboratory, including two
93 measures of FI: the AFI questionnaire (Nettle et al., 2019), and the USDA Food Insecurity scale
94 (Bickel et al., 2000). The USDA scale is the standard FI measure, but in general populations, most
95 people score zero. The AFI was designed to produce a more satisfactory distribution in general
96 population studies. It focusses on all experiences of food insecurity and irregularity, regardless of
97 their cause, whereas the USDA questionnaire focusses exclusively on food insecurity due to financial
98 constraints. The questionnaire also contained a number of measures of early-life experience that are
99 not analysed here.

100 *Procedure*

101 Participants were tested singly by one of two experimenters (SG and MR). Assignment to condition
102 was an alternate sign-up basis.

103 *Cola pre-task.* On arrival, participants consumed two cups containing 75g of Coca-Cola® Classic
104 (31.5kcal) and 75g of Pepsi (33kcal), then completed a 10-minute filler task in which they watched
105 video advertisements of the two brands and answered questions on their cola preferences. This is a
106 previously used method of equalising satiety levels prior to the taste test (Nettle et al., 2019; Wang and
107 Dvorak, 2010). Participants then rated their hunger, fullness and desire to eat on 7-point scales.

108 *SSES manipulation.* Participants next completed the experimental manipulation, based on Cheon and
109 Hong (2016). Each participant was shown an image of a ladder with rungs numbered 1 – 10,
110 representing UK society. In the low status condition, an adjacent body of text asked the participant to
111 compare herself to the people at the very top of the latter, think about how she was different from
112 those people, and then place herself on the ladder relative to them. Following this, the participant was
113 asked to imagine an interaction with a stranger from the top of the ladder. In the control condition,
114 participants placed themselves on the ladder without first comparing themselves to the people at the
115 top and no ladder position for the stranger in the imagined interaction was specified. After finishing

116 this, participants completed the PANAS measures of positive and negative affect (Watson et al.,
117 1988).

118 *Taste test.* Next, four standard pre-weighed plates of food were simultaneously presented by drawing
119 back curtains. The plates were positioned in a row and contained: milk chocolate buttons (69g,
120 516kcal/100g); cheese crackers (48g, 529kcal/100g); ready salted potato crisps (50g, 539kcal/100g);
121 and sweet popcorn (35g, 463kcal/100g). The quantities were chosen to balance available calories from
122 sweet food (518kcal) and savoury food (523kcal). Water was also presented.

123 For five minutes, participants were asked to evaluate each food on a 7-point scale, adding short
124 qualitative comments indicating what they liked and disliked about it. Once the five minutes had passed,
125 we distributed an additional packet of questionnaires, saying: ‘Please feel free to eat as much as you’d
126 like as we have to throw the food away between participants.’ The experimenter then withdrew for 10
127 minutes. Height (stadiometer, 0.5 cm precision) and weight (digital scales, 0.1 kg precision) were
128 recorded on conclusion of the session. Food plates were weighed following the session. Food weights
129 were converted to kilocalories using the nutritional information on the packaging.

130 *Data analysis*

131 For consumption, we had four outcome variables (kcal consumed of each of the four foods). We
132 therefore used multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) to examine whether FI, experimental
133 SSES condition, sex, and their interactions predicted the set of four consumption outcomes. Sex and
134 its interactions were included as previous studies have found sex differences in the response to FI. For
135 evaluation of the foods, we performed a parallel MANOVA with the four ratings of the foods as the
136 outcomes in place of the kcal consumed. Significant MANOVA findings were followed up with
137 single-outcome general linear models where appropriate. All analyses were carried out in R (R Core
138 Development Team, 2018), with an α level of 0.05 and two-sided tests throughout. The consumption
139 variables had positively skewed distributions and were log-transformed for analysis. Figures are based
140 on untransformed data.

141 The three hunger ratings prior to the taste test (rated hunger, rated fullness and rated desire to eat)
142 were after appropriate reversal all highly inter-correlated (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.82$). Henceforth they were
143 summed to provide a single variable referred to as current hunger.

144 We had two measures of FI, the AFI and USDA scores. These were correlated ($r = 0.57$, with USDA
145 score log transformed), but had very different distributions. For AFI score, only 5 participants scored
146 zero, and the central tendency was in the middle of the range. For USDA score, 90 participants (73%)
147 scored zero. We retained both measures for analysis, as they may carry somewhat different
148 information: AFI score as a continuous measure of the experience of food irregularity and
149 unpredictability in daily life; and USDA (which we dichotomised as ‘Secure’ (score of 0) or
150 ‘Insecure’ (score > 0)) as the standard marker of serious economically-driven FI. We therefore repeat
151 all models first using USDA FI, and then using AFI FI. Retaining two measures of FI increases
152 multiple testing and hence the false positive rate. We hence interpret significant results involving FI
153 with caution (see Discussion).

154 **Results**

155 *Descriptive statistics*

156 Descriptive statistics for the final study sample are shown in table 1. The amounts consumed of the
 157 different foods were all moderately positively correlated (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.73$), as were the
 158 evaluations of the foods (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.45$). The evaluation of the food was moderately correlated
 159 with the amount consumed in all cases (chocolate: $r = 0.37$, $p < 0.001$; crackers: $r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$;
 160 crisps: $r = 0.22$, $p = 0.01$; popcorn: $r = 0.46$, $p < 0.001$). Current hunger weakly or negligibly predicted
 161 consumption of the foods (chocolate: $r = 0.12$, $p = 0.18$; crackers: $r = 0.27$, $p = 0.002$; crisps: $r = 0.20$,
 162 $p = 0.03$; popcorn: $r = 0.16$, $p = 0.08$). Inclusion of current hunger as an additional predictor variable
 163 does not affect any of the results presented below.

164 *Calorie consumption*

165 Table 1 shows MANOVA results. For calorie consumption, using USDA as the FI measure, there was
 166 a significant interaction between SSES condition and FI in predicting consumption. To investigate the
 167 interaction, we split the data into food-secure and food-insecure participants, and performed separate
 168 MANOVAs with condition as the predictor. Amongst food-secure participants, there was a significant
 169 effect of condition ($F_{4, 85} = 3.84$, $p = 0.006$), with those in the low SSES condition consuming more
 170 than those in the control condition (figure 1). Amongst food-insecure participants, there was also a
 171 significant effect of condition ($F_{4, 28} = 2.85$, $p = 0.04$), but the difference was in the opposite direction
 172 (figure 1). Splitting into separate MANOVAs by condition instead of FI, in the control condition,
 173 there was a significant main effect of FI ($F_{4, 55} = 2.80$, $p = 0.03$), with food-insecure participants
 174 consuming more; whereas in the low SSES condition, the difference between food-secure and food-
 175 insecure participants was near-significantly in the opposite direction ($F_{4, 58} = 2.40$, $p = 0.06$).

176 The interaction between SSES condition and FI was not restricted to any one of the foods. In separate
 177 analyses of each outcome variable, the interaction term was significant or near-significant in all four
 178 cases (Chocolate: $B = 0.93$, 95% CI -0.01 – 1.87, $t = 1.95$, $p = 0.05$; Crackers: $B = 1.22$, 95% CI 0.35
 179 - 2.09, $t = 2.78$, $p = 0.006$; Crisps: $B = 1.43$, 95% CI 0.57 – 2.28, $t = 3.31$, $p = 0.001$; Popcorn: $B =$
 180 1.25 , 95% CI 0.29 – 2.21, $t = 2.58$, $p = 0.01$). Using continuous AFI score instead of USDA as the FI
 181 measure, the significant interaction of FI and SSES condition was not found (table 1). The main effect
 182 of condition was however significant.

183 *Evaluation of foods*

184 For evaluation of foods, results were similar whether USDA or AFI was used as the FI measure: there
 185 were significant main effects of both condition and FI on the set of ratings, and no interaction (table
 186 2). The pattern across the individual foods was complex (figure 2). The overall condition effect was
 187 driven by low SSES producing individually non-significant increases in the ratings of chocolate ($B =$
 188 0.44 , 95% CI -0.18 – 1.06, $t = 1.41$, $p = 0.16$), crackers ($B = 0.26$, 95% CI -0.28 – 0.80, $t = 0.94$, $p =$
 189 0.38), and crisps ($B = 0.33$, 95% CI -0.11 – 0.77, $t = 1.48$, $p = 0.14$), but a significant decrease in the
 190 rating of popcorn ($B = -0.78$, 95% CI -1.32 – 0.24, $t = -2.83$, $p = 0.005$). The FI effect (results shown
 191 for USDA) was driven by food-insecure participants giving significantly higher ratings to crisps ($B =$
 192 0.62 , 95% CI 0.11 – 1.11, $t = 2.44$, $p = 0.01$), non-significantly higher ratings to crackers ($B = 0.19$,
 193 95% CI -0.42 – 0.81, $t = 0.63$, $p = 0.53$) and popcorn ($B = 0.42$, 95% CI -0.19 – 1.03, $t = 1.37$, $p =$
 194 0.17), but non-significantly lower ratings to chocolate ($B = -0.34$, 95% CI -1.03 – 0.35, $t = -0.97$, $p =$
 195 0.33).

196

197 **Discussion**

198 We measured opportunistic snack food consumption, and the evaluation of snack foods, in a sample
199 of participants where baseline FI was known, and SSES was experimentally manipulated using a
200 recently published method. Our first goal was to replicate the finding that experimental SSES
201 manipulation affects consumption. We confirmed that it did. For the food-secure participants (who
202 constituted the majority of the sample), the effect was as described in previous studies (Bratanova et
203 al., 2016; Cardel et al., 2015; Cheon and Hong, 2016; Sim et al., 2018a): consumption was higher
204 across the range of foods in the low status than the control condition. Our second goal was to replicate
205 the finding that food-insecure participants consume more when given an opportunity to do so freely
206 (Nettle et al., 2019; Stinson et al., 2018). Here, the replication was partial. In the control condition,
207 food-insecure participants did indeed consume significantly more than food-secure participants.
208 However, our prediction was that this would be true for the female but not male participants, and we
209 found no interaction by sex. This could be a power issue given the unbalanced sex composition of the
210 sample. Moreover, the effects involving FI were only significant using the USDA measure, not AFI.
211 In our previous comparable study (Nettle et al., 2019), the significant FI effects were found using AFI
212 rather than USDA (though see Stinson et al., 2018 for significant FI effects using the USDA
213 measure). However, even correcting for two rounds of multiple testing given our two FI measures, the
214 effects involving FI would be deemed significant by conventional criteria.

215 Our most striking finding, however, was that FI and experimentally-induced low SSES interacted
216 strongly. It was not just that evoking SSES produced a smaller increase in consumption amongst
217 food-insecure participants, as might be expected through a ceiling effect given that consumption by
218 food-insecure participants was already high in the control condition. Rather, in food-insecure
219 participants, consumption across the range of foods was significantly reduced in the low SSES
220 condition compared to control. We did not predict the reversal a priori; there is the multiple-FI-
221 measure issue mentioned above; and the number of USDA food-insecure participants was small (33).
222 We therefore consider the finding exploratory and as requiring further investigation. As well as
223 determining whether the interaction is robust, such investigation would need to explore why it occurs.
224 It is possible that food-insecure participants are self-conscious about eating and weight, so that when
225 faced with a negative status manipulation, respond by over-riding an automatic tendency to increase
226 eating, producing a deliberate over-compensation in the opposite direction. However, this remains a
227 speculation on our part, since we had no measure of eating restraint or self-consciousness about eating
228 and weight. We did measure negative and positive affect, but the only relationships of these measures
229 to other study variables was that baseline food-insecure participants had higher levels of negative
230 affect (full analyses not shown).

231 FI and low SSES were associated with differences in the evaluation of foods. This lends partial
232 support to the hypothesis that the psychological mechanisms underlying FI and SSES effects on
233 consumption involve changes in the hedonic value of food. However, the effects were small and hard
234 to interpret. Although the average rating across all four foods was higher in the low SSES condition
235 than the control condition, and higher amongst food-insecure than food-secure participants, there was
236 heterogeneity across the foods, with one food showing the reversed pattern in each case. Moreover,
237 the effects on evaluations were additive, rather than the interaction seen for consumption. Thus, the
238 precise changes in hedonic properties of food that are associated with low SSES and FI, as well as
239 their roles in mediating changes in consumption, require further investigation.

240

241 **Author contributions**

242 All four authors conceived and designed the study collaboratively. SG and MR conducted the
 243 experimental sessions and collated the data. SG, MR and DN performed the data analysis. SG and MR
 244 wrote first drafts of the paper. DN and MB revised the paper for content.

245 **Conflicts of interests**

246 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interests.

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- 296

297 Table 1. Descriptive statistics for the main study variables.

Variable	Mean	Standard deviation
Age	30.66	16.66
FI (USDA)	Secure 90 Insecure 33	
FI (AFI score)	6.05	4.11
Current hunger	10.71	4.01
Chocolate consumption (kcal)	88.34	84.93
Cracker consumption (kcal)	51.92	56.06
Crisp consumption (kcal)	46.26	51
Popcorn consumption (kcal)	24.78	33.05
Evaluation of chocolate	5.21	1.72
Evaluation of crackers	5.07	1.47
Evaluation of crisps	5.11	1.27
Evaluation of popcorn	4.96	1.56

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300 Table 2. MANOVA results .

Calorie consumption						
	Using USDA FI status			Using AFI score		
Predictor	F	df	p-value	F	df	p-value
Condition	3.74	4, 112	0.007*	3.67	4, 112	0.008*
FI	1.15	4, 112	0.33	0.96	4, 112	0.43
Sex	0.32	4, 112	0.87	0.28	4, 112	0.89
Condition * FI	3.46	4, 112	0.01*	0.54	4, 112	0.71
Condition * Sex	2.10	4, 112	0.09	1.88	4, 112	0.12
Sex * FI	0.99	4, 112	0.42	1.01	4, 112	0.41
Condition * Sex * FI	2.01	4, 112	0.10	0.86	4, 112	0.49
Evaluation of foods						
	Using USDA FI status	Using AFI score				
Predictor	F	df	p-value	F	df	p-value
Condition	2.62	4, 105	0.04*	2.61	4, 105	0.04*
FI	2.56	4, 105	0.04*	2.49	4, 105	0.048*
Sex	0.54	4, 105	0.71	0.52	4, 105	0.72
Condition * FI	1.25	4, 105	0.29	0.50	4, 105	0.73
Condition * Sex	0.97	4, 105	0.43	1.04	4, 105	0.39
Sex * FI	1.26	4, 105	0.29	1.81	4, 105	0.13
Condition * Sex * FI	2.09	4, 105	0.09	1.34	4, 105	0.26

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305 Figure 1. Calorie consumption by food insecurity status (USDA) and experimental SSES condition.

306 Bars are broken into consumption of the four constituent foods. Error bars represent one \pm 1 standard

307 error of total consumption.

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310 Figure 2. Mean evaluations of the foods: (A) by SSES condition; (B) by USDA food insecurity status.

311 Error bars represent ± 1 standard error.